

IMPACT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE INCIDENCE OF VISCERAL LEISHMANIASIS IN BIHAR, INDIA

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Abstract

The present work confirm that burden of Kala-azar is disproportionately borne by vulnerable and marginalized groups. Kala-azar is most entrenched in the poorest communities. Elimination of Kala-azar is directly related to poverty alleviation because if the poverty incidence reduces, it will lead to reduction of Kala-azar incidence. The strategy for disease control or elimination should shift from traditional disease-centered approaches to a holistic approach that can break the links between poverty and Kala-azar.

Key word: Kala-azar, Socio-Economic Factors, Harwa Jabbar Jheel

INTRODUCTION

Kala azar (Visceral leishmaniasis) is a neglected tropical disease (NTD) which can be fatal if left untreated. It is transmitted by the bite of a sand fly and is characterised by prolonged fever, enlarged spleen, substantial weight loss and progressive anemia.

Bihar is the epicentre of kala azar in India, where 33 out of 38 districts are affected. The population at risk is nearly 35 million in approximately 11,500 villages spread over 429 provincial blocks.

Leishmaniasis is an infection caused by a parasite that is spread to people through the bite of the female phlebotomine sand fly. The parasite exists in many tropical and temperate countries. Cases in the United States are almost always imported from other countries by travelers or immigrants. Epidemics occur when people are displaced into affected regions through war or migration or when people in affected regions experience high rates of disease or malnutrition.

Out of 38 districts of Bihar, 33 are affected with kala-azar especially the Araria, Purnea, Kisanganj and Madhepura districts are highly affected.

The eradication of this dreadful disease from the State is very important and the present Govt. has also shown willingness and taken certain steps. The Union health minister Dr Harsh Vardhan has vowed to eliminate kala-azar from Bihar and other parts of the country by 2015. For this, the ministry will take a slew of steps including providing Ambisome injection that cures the disease with a single shot. Bihar, incidentally, accounts for 80% kala-azar cases in the world, with 33 districts of the state affected by the disease. The present investigation was done to know the socio-economic status of the effected people, which will be useful in eradication of kala-azar from the state.

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Material and Methods

The field study was made in the disease endemic villages in the district of Araria, Purnea, Kisanganj and Madhepura. The study was conducted in a total of 200 villages (50 villages in each district). In each district 50 beneficiaries were selected to carry out the study.

Results and Discussion

Table : The summary of the findings

Sl.no	Variables	Percentage
Distribution of Respondents according to age group		
1	Age below – 20	12.95
2	20 – 29	28.55
3	30 – 39	21.7
4	40 – 49	17.9
5	Above – 49	18.9
Distribution of Respondents according to occupational status		
6	Farmers	45.4
7	Civil servants	11.1
8	Traders/businessman	10.25
9	House wives	13.9
10	Students	19.35
Distribution of Respondents according to Area of Residence.		
11	Rural	62.5
12	Urban (Outskirts)	20.0
13	Urban (Congested Colonies)	17.5
Distribution of Respondents according to Educational Status.		
14	No formal education	23.9
15	Higher education	19.5
16	Primary education	22.45
17	Secondary education	20.7
18	Vocational/ profesional	13.45
Respondents understanding about the Meaning of Kala-azar.		
19	Right	45.05
20	Wrong	42.05
21	No idea	12.9
Respondents' undertaking about the Meaning symptoms of Kala-azar.		
22	Right	80.6
23	Partial	11.35
24	Wrong	6.5
25	No idea	1.55
Respondents' Perception for the Causes of Kala-azar		
26	Natural cause	3.5
27	Mosquito	61.4
28	Poor environmental conditions	15.65
29	Poor healthcare delivery	11.2
30	Poverty/poor environmental condition	8.25
Frequency of Attacks of Kala-azar		
31	- at below 20 years	36.5
32	- at 21 – 30 years	33.3

33	- 31 – 40 years	13.5
34	- at 41 – 50 years	10.25
35	- above 51 years	6.75
Types of Kala-azar Treatment Preferred by the respondents.		
36	Ojha/Priest	3.05
37	Herbal/ Vaida clinic	19.29
38	Private doctor	23.43
39	Hospital	33.71
40	Vaida/Chemist	2.33
41	Vaida/ Chemist/Doctor	5.58
42	Vaida/Chemist/Hospital	7.61

DISCUSSION

Kala-azar is a slow progressing indigenous disease caused by a protozoan parasite of genus *Leishmania*. In India *Leishmania donovani* is the only parasite causing this disease. The parasite primarily infects reticuloendothelial system and may be found in abundance in bone marrow, spleen and liver.

This study is probably an attempt to assess the association of various socioeconomic and environmental factors with occurrence of kala-azar. It was previously reported that most kala-azar patients had incomes less than \$1 per day (65 Indian Rupees). Such poverty may not be a risk factor for kala-azar, but it can lead to malnutrition, poor housing conditions, lack of preventive measures in the form of sanitation and bed nets, and illiteracy. Thus, poverty could be a major determinant for continued transmission of Kala-azar in Bihar and other parts of India.

A history of other diseases such as tuberculosis, hepatitis, or viral fever in the past year has a significant impact on the occurrence of kala-azar because these diseases may reduce the immune status of the host. The low immunity of the host increases the risk of being infected with *L. donovani*. Multiple cases of kala-azar in a family have been reported from Bihar. In this study, it was observed that the risk of kala-azar was higher among cases with a history of kala-azar among the family members in the past year compared with those cases with no history of kala-azar among family members. The presence of kala-azar cases in the family might aid the transmission of this disease in the presence of sand fly vectors and other conditions favorable for completion of transmission cycle within the house.

The use of mud for wall construction or for plastering walls in rural areas was found to be significantly associated with kala-azar, a finding previously reported in other studies (Thang 2000, Desjeux 1996) *Phlebotomus argentipes* sand flies are commonly found in cracks and crevices of mud walls, mud-plastered walls, or unplastered brick walls in rural areas of Bihar. These endophagic sand flies usually breed inside cowsheds and human dwellings, especially inside cracks and crevices of walls where optimum temperature and humidity are available (Joshi 2008). Mud walls can retain moisture for many months after the rainy season, which further increases favorable conditions for sand fly breeding and resting. Filling of cracks and crevices in walls with a mixture of lime and mud have been advocated as an ecologic approach for the control of *P. argentipes* inside houses (Kendall 2011).

The present study was to study the socio-economic condition of the patients of kalaazar through questionnaire. The results revealed that the respondents of age group of 20-29 years were more active and responded more followed by the age group of 30-39, above 49 years and 40-49 years. The male was more active than female may be due to easily accessible. It can be observed here that the male respondents almost doubled the female respondents. This might not be unconnected with the fact that males are usually more accessible than

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female counterparts. In fact sometimes when female were approached with the questionnaires they declined collecting and as such were not insisted upon, since collecting and filling questionnaire should be voluntary and not compulsory. The table reveals that all the respondents were predominantly either Hindus or Muslims, with Muslims having higher participation.

Occupational status of the respondents shows that the study has fairly cut across different professions. However, farmers have the largest percentage (45.4%); this could be as a result that farmers are more accessible than other categories of respondents. The educational attainment of the respondents was found to be rather high, since about 50 percent of the total respondents were educated beyond the primary school level . The respondent good educational background may likely support their perceptions about the aetiology and treatment of Kala-azar on the assumption that educated people tend to embrace knowledge of new innovation and understand new ideas better.

The understanding of the respondents about the meaning of Kala-azar is rather high, wrongly, about 42 percent offered only an incorrect meaning of Kala-azar and about 12.9 percent have no idea about the meaning of Kala-azar. Out of the total respondents only 901 representing 45.05% offered the correct meaning of Kala-azar . This means that majority of the people in Project area district, although are aware of Kala-azar but their understanding about the meaning of the disease is low. The results also shows that most of the respondents 80.6% understood the symptoms of Kala-azar. Some 11.35% respondents could not state the symptoms of the disease correctly and only 1.55% had no idea about the symptoms of Kala-azar. It could be observed here that the perception of the respondents with respect to their understanding about the symptoms of Kala-azar is very high. The findings reveals that the perception of the respondents about the causes of Kala-azar in project district, almost half of the total respondents had the opinion that the Kala-azar as a disease is caused by mosquitoes . This is a good perception, since Kala-azar parasites are transmitted from one person to another by sand fly (very similar to mosquitoes for common people) . Therefore, if the environment is kept clean there will be no breeding grounds for the sandfly and there will be no Kala-azar. Of the 870 who have experienced Kala-azar attacks, shows the frequency of attack. It was reported that the rising all-case mortality rate among children is attributable directly to Kala-azar (Frontline, 2005). Kala-azar is a disease of poverty and despite all the knowledge about its aetiology, biochemistry and immunology very little progress has been made in its treatment at a community level (Ridley, 2002). It was observed that about 36.5% suffered from the attack of Kala-azar at least within below 20 years of age. This is perhaps as a result of risk taking behavior. The second large percentage that suffered from Kala-azar attack at least once in their life was about 33.3% fall within the age category of below 21-30 years. This is an age group of childhood and adolescence in which Kala-azar is responsible for 25 percent in infant mortality and 30% of all childhood deaths (WHO, 2000) 31.5% suffered Kala-azar attack at least, once in their life within the age group 31 to 40 years, 10.25% suffered Kala-azar attack at least once in their life, within the age group of 41 to 50 years, whereas only 6.75% suffered Kala-azar attack at an age category of above 51 years. People of such age usually take necessary health measures since they know that their immune system start to weaken.

The result also revealed that 20% respondents suffered from Kala-azar attacks every month and 7% were in Kala-azar attack always. This could be true because the problems of controlling Kala-azar in project district as in other districts where the situation is aggravated inadequate health structures and poor socioeconomics conditions. The situation has become even more complex over the last few years with the increase in resistance to the drug normally used to combat the parasites that cause the disease (WHO, 2005).

Findings reveals the type of treatment preferred by the respondents whenever they were attacked by Kala-azar. 19.29% preferred to visit vaidia clinic only for the treatment of Kala-azar. This could be due to the fact that, plants have formed the basis for the treatment of diseases in traditional medical system for thousand years and continue to play a major role in the primary healthcare delivery of about (80%) of the world's population (WHO, 1986). 3.43% respondents preferred to visit private doctors for the treatment of Kala-azar, while 33.71% preferred

to visit hospital for the treatment of Kala-azar. This means that only about 34% of the total respondents preferred to see doctors for the diagnosis and prescription of medication before starting treatment of Kala-azar 23 respondents (2%) preferred to go to local/ traditional clinic for the treatment of Kala-azar and if it fails then, they go to doctors. 19.29% preferred to visit herbal clinic for Kala-azar treatment, if the treatment fails then they go to pharmacy/chemist, if they do not succeed then they go to hospital as a last resort. 5.58% respondents preferred to visit pharmacy/chemist at the beginning, if they were not successful then they go to hospital. The respondents attitude to completion of Kala-azar treatment. The result suggested the need for improved patients counseling by the health professionals on the importance of completing treatment, since incomplete treatment will lead to rapid increase in resistance to anti-Kala-azar drugs by the Kala-azar causative agents. Table revealed the distribution of the respondents according to their individual profession. The result also tallied with the responses of the general public concerning whom they attend to in case of Kala-azar attacks. The findings also reveals the various opinions on conducting Kala-azar parasites test before starting treatment. It could be observed from the results that the opinions of some of the respondents will be very detrimental to the management of Kala-azar in district. Since without conducting Kala-azar parasites test, it will be difficult to give proper treatment. The present condition of our laboratories should also be looked in to, since many of the respondents stated that the test is not reliable. This may be as a result of expired reagents or obsolete equipment used for conducting the test. It could be observed here that all the respondents were either adopting very effective method of Kala-azar treatment or some of them are not sincere enough to say the truth, since we know as a fact that, the number of effective drugs available to treat Kala-azar small and the rate at which resistance is growing is outpacing the development of new antiKala-azars (Frontline, 2005). Table reveals the various reasons responsible for Kala-azar treatment failure as opined by the respondents. The absence of adequate health services results in recourse to self administration of drugs often with incomplete treatment: and this is a major factor in the increase in resistance of the respondents have the opinion that poor administration of medication is responsible for treatment failure and only about 17 percent have the opinion that poor attitude to treatment follow-up is responsible for treatment failure. Findings also reveals various opinions, on how Kala-azar can be controlled. 31.68% respondents associated the control of the disease with good environmental sanitation, while 25.08 have the opinion that, good health delivery will give effective control. However, none had accepted religious belief only.

The findings confirm that burden of Kala-azar is disproportionately borne by vulnerable and marginalized groups. Kala-azar is most entrenched in the poorest communities. Elimination of Kala-azar is directly related to poverty alleviation because if the poverty incidence reduces, it will lead to reduction of Kala-azar incidence. The strategy for disease control or elimination should shift from traditional disease-centered approaches to a holistic approach that can break the links between poverty and Kala-azar.

The present investigation will be useful to know the socio-economic status of the most effected people and improvement in the socio-economic status and creating awareness will be important tool for eradication of kalazar from the state.

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